

Specialized Ribosomes in Translation and Gene Regulation

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Abstract

Composed of two subunits, the ribosome is the machinery that translates the genetic code in mRNA to produce polypeptides across species. Biochemically comprising of ribonucleic acid as the catalytic core and ribosomal proteins which are essential for viability, were thought to be identical across species. Many studies in the past have suggested variation in the composition of ribosomes which accord them a special feature of selective translation of certain mRNAs. Here we review old and recent literatures that presented variation in ribosomal composition which may dictate the types of mRNAs they translate and hence the nature of proteins they produce.

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Introduction

The ribosome, a large ribonucleoprotein particle, is composed of two subunits in all species and comprises nearly two thirds ribosomal RNA (rRNA) and one third ribosomal proteins (RPs) (Alberts *et al.*, 2008). The two subunits are the large ribosomal subunit (50S in prokaryotes and 60S in eukaryotes) and the small ribosomal subunit (30S in prokaryotes and 40S in eukaryotes). The 60S subunit consist of three rRNAs, 28S (25S in yeast, 3392 nt), 5.8S (158 nt) and 5S (121 nt) and 45 ribosomal proteins where as the small subunit is made up of 18S (1798 nt) and 32 ribosomal proteins. The large subunit contains the peptidyl transferase centre, which catalyzes peptide bond formation between amino acids. The small subunit contains the decoding domain, responsible for decoding the mRNA message, contained within the open reading frame (ORF), by scanning its codons with an initiator tRNA anticodon (Maguire and Zimmermann, 2001).

Biogenesis of ribosomes is a conserved, essential process in eukaryotic cells. The pathway for ribosome synthesis is a complex and highly coordinated multi-step process which utilises hundreds of genes that are required to produce functional ribosomal RNAs (rRNAs) and the associated ribosomal proteins (RPs). In eukaryotic organisms, this process occurs in the nucleolus, a compartment located in the nucleus (Tschochner and Hurt, 2003; Thomson *et al.*, 2013). Within the nucleolus, this coordinated process occurs in the three sub-nucleolar regions, the fibrillar centre (FC), dense fibrillar centres (DFC) and the granular component (GC) (Shaw and Brown, 2012).

Ribosome biogenesis has been well-studied over the past three to four decades, with a good understanding of the pathway coming from a study in the yeast, *S. cerevisiae* (Li *et al.*, 2009). The process requires the action and coordination of all three RNA polymerases (I, II and III) and begins with transcription of the rRNA genes that encode the 18S, 5.8S and 28S (25S in yeast) rRNAs. These rRNA genes are separated within their sequences by internal transcribed spacer (ITS) sequences and their 5' and 3' ends are flanked by external transcribed spacers (ETS) (Tschochner and Hurt, 2003). The 28S, 18S and 5.8S are transcribed from rDNA repeats by Pol I in the nucleolar organiser regions (NORs) as a polycistronic pre-rRNA in the DFC and at the peripheral regions of the FC of the

nucleolus (Hozak *et al.*, 1994; Dunder and Raška, 1993). The 5S rRNA is transcribed by Pol III in the GC region (Dunder and Raška, 1993) and the RP genes transcribed by Pol II (Figure 1). Ribosomal proteins are synthesised in the cytoplasm and are rapidly imported to the nucleus where they associate with rRNA to form the pre-ribosomal subunits (Lam *et al.*, 2007; Tschochner and Hurt, 2003).

Figure 1. Schematic of the eukaryotic ribosome biogenesis. The rRNAs 18S, 5.8S and 28S (25S in yeast) are transcribed by Pol I in the DFC and possibly at the peripheral area of the FC whereas 5S is transcribed separately by Pol III. Further processing and assembly occur in the nucleus. RPs genes are transcribed in the nucleus and translated in the cytoplasm by the ribosome. The RPs are then imported to the nucleolus where they mostly assemble on the pre-rRNA co-transcriptionally. Some of the RPs assembles on the ribosome in the cytoplasm during the last maturation steps.

Specialized Ribosomes

Although ribosomes were thought to be identical across an organism’s cell types, recent studies are increasingly indicating that there are variations in composition between individual ribosomes and that this feature may have a significant role in defining the kind of proteins they produce (Xue and Barna, 2012; Gilbert, 2011; Moll and Engelberg-Kulka, 2012). An early study that demonstrated the existence of specialized ribosomes in translation was reported nearly 30 years ago in *E. coli* (Hui and de Boer, 1987). This study demonstrated that some modified ribosomes, with altered Shine-Delgarno (SD) sequences, were able to translate some mutated mRNAs. More recently, a study in *E. coli*

reported the translation of leaderless mRNAs by a group of ribosomes that are modified by the MazF toxin (Vesper *et al.*, 2011; Moll and Engelberg-Kulka, 2012; Filipovska and Rackham, 2013). The MazF toxin is an endoribonuclease produced from the stress-induced toxin-antitoxin (TA) module Maz EF, that acts on both single stranded mRNA and the 16S rRNA of the bacterial 30S ribosome subunit, cutting them at the ACA codon (Vesper *et al.*, 2011). This action generates leaderless mRNAs (lmRNAs) and a unique 30S subunit ribosome with a 16S that is 43 nucleotides shorter at the 3' end. This 30S can form a translation competent ribosome that preferentially translates lmRNAs (Moll and Engelberg-Kulka, 2012; Vesper *et al.*, 2011). Interestingly, lmRNAs are found in all kingdoms of life (Janssen, 1993). Additionally, some observations revealed that many mRNAs possess segments that are complementary to a sequence within either the 18S or 28S, suggesting the possibility of a mechanism that allows direct interaction between mRNAs and ribosomal subunits through base pairing of these complementary sequences (Mauro and Edelman, 2007). Furthermore, eukaryotic ribosomes were reported to differ in rRNA sequences and RPs composition at different developmental stages and in particular cells or tissues (Ramagopal, 1992). This led to the hypothesis that there exists an array of structurally different ribosomes that can translate a specific set of mRNAs (Mauro and Edelman, 2007).

Previous studies have reported that heterogeneity in RP composition within a ribosome may confer these specialized functions in translation, and may regulate the translation of a subset of mRNAs by controlling access to the binding sites within the rRNA (Mauro and Edelman, 2002; Mauro and Edelman, 2007). Similarly, the degree of expression of several RPs was found to differ in different cell types, growth conditions or developmental stages in *D. discoideum*, *Arabidopsis thaliana*, *D. melanogaster* and human cells (Weijers *et al.*, 2001; Ramagopal, 1990; Filipovska and Rackham, 2013; Kondrashov *et al.*, 2011). For example in *Arabidopsis*, one ribosomal protein of the small subunit, Rps5, has two duplicates, Rps5A and Rps5B, of which Rps5A is the most highly expressed in actively dividing cells, whereas the Rps5B is expressed in differentiating cells (Weijers *et al.*, 2001). In translation, Rps25 was reported to be required for IRES-mediated translation initiation and 40S ribosomal subunits devoid of Rps25 could not initiate translation via an IRES element (Nishiyama *et al.*, 2007; Muhs *et al.*, 2011). Similarly, an Rpl38 mutation in mice was found to show a minimal effect in general translation inhibition but selectively inhibits the translation of Homeobox (Hox) mRNAs (Filipovska and Rackham, 2013; Barna, 2013). Recently, a ribosomal protein of the large subunit, Rpl40, that on the whole is not required for general cellular mRNA cap-dependent translation initiation, was reported to be essential for initiating translation in a number of *Mononegavirales* viruses, for example vesicular stomatitis virus cap-dependent mRNA translation, and completely dispensable for IRES-mediated translation of other viral mRNAs (Lee *et al.*, 2013; Barna, 2013). This suggested that the Rpl40 translation dependent pathway is involved in stress responses. Further evidence supporting this view came from a survey of protein expression in mice using sub-cellular fractionation coupled with tandem mass spectrometry-base shotgun sequencing (Kislinger *et al.*, 2006). Analysing this data with a web-browser interface revealed that certain RPs were present in all tissues examined whereas others were not always detected (Kislinger *et al.*, 2006). Other RPs were found to be more abundant in particular tissues, or were less abundant or completely absent in other tissues. For example Rps3 and Rps7 were observed in all tissues but Rps6, which was found to be abundant in the brain, kidney and liver has a lower level in the lungs and is completely absent in the heart (Mauro and Edelman, 2007). Similarly, we have observed in our laboratory that endogenously YFP-tagged Rpl40, which was found to be abundant in many tissues and cell types, is particularly concentrated in larval *Drosophila* adult midgut progenitor cells (AMPs) but absent in differentiated enterocytes and enteroendocrine cells (Akilu Abdullahi, 2013). Taken together, these data indicate that the composition of ribosomes is of great importance in determining the sets of mRNAs they translate.

Conclusion

Although the basic biochemical structural components of ribosomes remain the same, many studies revealed certain variations in composition across individual ribosomes and that difference may have a significant role in determining the kind of mRNA they engage in translation and hence the proteins

they produce. Future developments in the study of structural composition of ribosomes will unravel more complexity and heterogeneity of ribosomes and the protein products they synthesize.

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